

Impacts of COVID-19 on the Education, Social Life and Mental Health of University Students in Bangladesh

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Abstract: As a result of COVID-19 pandemic, people from all sectors of the country particularly Bangladeshi students have been suffered a lot. Academic performance, everyday activities and regular daily life of students were hindered mostly when student's mental health was significantly influenced by home quarantine, physical distance and other negative circumstances. This online cross-sectional survey was conducted with 489 university students to assess the social and mental health impact of COVID-19 among university students in Bangladesh where chi-square test was used to find out the relationship between social & mental health indicators and educational institutions. This study explored that most of the students spent their time during pandemic by using social media (Facebook) (36.5%), an alarming portion (47.6%) of students (girls) were forced by their family stop studying to get married. In addition, students (28.5%) engaged quarrels with their family and parents as well as students (14.6%) involve in smoking during COVID-19 pandemic. Along with these, during COVID-19 pandemic students suffer from frustration (90%), indecision problem (64.8%), mental stress (42.5%), loneliness (72.7%), mood swing (75.5%) and even students (18%) tried to commit suicide at that time. Most of the students acquired the bad habit of over sleeping (71.3%), over thinking (76.9%) and 74.9% lost their interest from their preferred work also. The results reflected that COVID-19 pandemic has strong negative social and mental health impacts on the university students. So government and academic institutions must prioritize providing students with high-quality care in order to meet their needs both academically and personally.

Keywords: COVID-19, Education, Social Life, Mental Health, Depression, Frustration, Mental Stress, University Students, Bangladesh.

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Introduction

It was in late 2019 that the globe was alerted to an outbreak of coronavirus infection (COVID-19) that originated in Wuhan, China's Hubei region (Xiang et al. 2020). On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the new coronavirus (2019-nCoV) a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) (World Health Organization, 2020). The pandemic has been a threat to human wellbeing worldwide, notably in

Bangladesh when COVID-19 was first introduced to Bangladesh on March 8, 2020. The Bangladeshi government issued a nationwide lockdown from March 26 to prevent the spread of the disease and limit infection danger (Anwar et al., 2020). Because of covid-19, students' academics, daily routines, and habits may be interrupted, and their mental health may be harmed. Students' mental health is likely to be negatively impacted by home quarantine, physical/spatial distance, and other constraints (Rubin

& Wessely, 2020) (Brooks et al., 2020). According to stress and risk perception theories, public health crises can provoke strong negative feelings in those involved in them. COVID-19-related stressors for students may include health problems resulting from an increase in cases, the consequences of distancing/isolation measures, and disruptions in commencing classes and taking exams (Gupta & Goplani, 2020). Students in the quarantine may experience sentiments of pessimism, dread of death, and dissatisfaction due to these factors (Santamara et al., 2021).

The pandemic of COVID-19 has created social and mental problem among students as well as hampered the academic progress of students. Many students and teachers are impacted by school closures and other limitations, which affect billions of people. COVID-19's social isolation and other restrictions may lead to psychological problems such as worry and terror, severely impacting students' and their parents' well-being (Ozer, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has led to the temporary closure of many educational institutions worldwide. More than 60 percent of the world's student population is affected by these nationwide closures. More than 1.5 billion students worldwide have been impacted by educational institution closures (Emon et al., 2020). As of March 2020, Bangladesh has indicated that it will shut down all its institutions, affecting an estimated 40 million students (The Business Standard, 2020). For 17 months already, these schools have substantially impacted the educational, social, and mental health of students across the country (Rouf et al., 2022). This rapid change has affected students of all ages on such a big scale (Hasan and Bao, 2020). Travel restrictions and educational institution closures across the country are projected to substantially impact students' education, social lives, and mental health (Odriozola-gonzalez et al., 2020). In addition, Lee (2020) estimates that 1.5 billion students worldwide are currently unable to obtain a basic education, which harms their mental health. Disturbed sleep and social isolation have also contributed to students' mental health issues, as has a shift in daily routine (Cao et al. 2020).

Mental health and academic growth might be significantly impacted by a delay in reopening educational establishments (Chandasiri, 2020). Students' study and work habits were disrupted and deteriorated over the lengthy home quarantine period, increasing stress and dysfunctional learning practices (Meo et al., 2020). During pre-COVID-19 periods, a previous survey found that 52.2 percent of Bangladeshi university students experienced moderate to extremely severe depression, 58.1 percent of students reported anxiety, and 24.9 percent reported tension (Mamun et al., 2019). Some social and mental health problem has been seen among the Bangladeshi students during the pandemic. Loneliness, over thinking, oversleeping, suffering indecision, thinking negatively, lost interest from preferred work as well as by being depressed doing smoking were the major mental health problems. As the coronavirus pandemic spreads, students may become increasingly reliant on their mobile devices and the Internet, increasing social media addiction. Due to rising Internet and social media use, the pandemic scenario and its effects on their mental health pose a double threat. During the pandemic students were passing their time by reading books, by doing household work, by doing household work, by playing online games and by using social media. During the COVID-19 outbreak in Wuhan, social media use appears to have taken a toll on users' mental health (Gao et al., 2020).

According to research, students with solid and familial relations are less likely to suffer from depression (Cao et al., 2020; Wu et al., 2020). Most of the students were urged by their family especially for girls to stop their study and for getting marry to recover this uncertain future. Consequently students were engaged quarrels with their parents and family members during COVID pandemic. During this epidemic, students' mental health must retain healthy family relationships, as many will be forced to spend more time at home with their families to comply with social isolation and distancing measures (Wu et al., 2020). Families may be strained if students cannot maintain healthy relationships with their families while being confined to their homes during this uncertain and stressful time. Considering that Facebook is one of the most popular social media sites, it is not surprising that it has seen a 70% rise in time spent and a 50% increase in messages since the outbreak (Schultz & Parikh, 2020). Social media using increased during the pandemic than before COVID19. Addiction to social media manifests as various symptoms, including an obsession with using it, developing tolerance signs, and refusing to give up using it despite the adverse effects (Cheng et al., 2022). COVID-19 has had an impact on Bangladeshi university education as well. Many publications have been written on the educational implications of the COVID-19 test, but as far as the researchers know, very little work has been done on the social and mental effects of this assessment on Bangladeshi university students regarding social and psychological impacts on education. Consequently, the importance of evaluating data on the impact of COVID-19 on Bangladeshi higher education and its students must be gathered. Such a study is expected to quantify the social and psychological effects of an unforeseen emergency on students and create and implement effective interventions and techniques to alleviate the mental health of people at large. Bangladeshi university students were the subject of this research, which aims to address the social and psychological impacts which they face regarding education.

Methodology

Data Collection Procedure

A web based cross-sectional survey was conducted in mid-2021 to assess the mental and social impacts of COVID-19 among university students in Bangladesh. Data collection takes place from June 2020 to December 2020. Questionnaire has been converted from English to Bengali for easy understanding from respondents' point of view. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, there were not possible to collect data through a face-to-face interview. We collected data by Google form. An online questionnaire was designed for the survey to collect information from the participants. The inclusion criteria included: being a university student with internet access and living in Bangladesh during the study period. Participants who are not university students, not willing to participate, and missing data were excluded from the study. On the very first page of the web-based survey, participants were required to give their written consent by selecting either yes or no in response to the consent question. The survey took approximately 15/20minutes to complete. Participation in this survey was on a volunteer basis and random as well. After removing incomplete data, there were a total of 489 responses whos were current university students and recently graduated from university as well as willing to participate in the study. A convenience sampling has been used to reach survey participants.

Measure

There are four factors that we addressed in this questionnaire: education, family life, daily life, and mental health. The first section was related to the consent statement of the participants. The second section was Socio demographic related question. The third section was mental health related question. following section contained questions about the impacts of COVID-19 on students mental health; for example, (mental stress, frustration, depression, thinking about suicide, over sleeping and thinking, negative thinking, mood swing, loneliness, indecision problem, taking drug for mental stress relief, losing interest from preferred work and duration of sleeping during & before COVID-19 pandemic etc. The fourth section covered the effects of COVID-19 on students' social lives, which included questions about the time they spent on social media, student's family relationship, family force in stopping study to get married (girls), spending COVID time, smoking status, duration of sleeping and social media usage (Facebook) during COVID period as social indicators. Questionnaire has been developed based on open-ended, multiple-choice, and Likert scale-

type questions etc.

Participants

To obtain enough data to address the research question, data were collected from 489 students for the research employing convenience sampling. They were the students of four universities such as public university, private university. National university and Dhaka University affiliated 7 colleges. Among the 489 students, 345 were male students, and 144 were female. Sample Students were from running honor's and master's students as well as recently master's completed students.

Data Analysis

Immediately after conducting the interviews, all the recorded excel data sheets were enter into the R programming to code and analysis the data. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages) were computed for the prevalence. After that, the chi-square test was used to find out the relationship between mental health and social health related questions and educational institutions. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 01: Socio Demographic Background of the Respondents

Variable	Number (n=489)	Percentage
Gender		
Male	345	70.5
Female	144	29.5
Educational Institution		
DU Affiliated Seven College	104	21.3
National University	113	23.1
Private University	89	18.2
Public University	183	37.4
Living Area		
Dhaka City	305	62.8
Divisional City	74	14.7
Village	110	22.5
Monthly Family Income		
Upper Class (Above 30000 Taka)	140	29
Middle Class (Between 15000-30000 Taka)	188	39.1
Lower Middle Class (Below 15000 Taka)	161	31.9
Marital Status		
Married	49	9.4
Unmarried	440	90.6
Educational Level		
Honor's	371	76.1
Master's	78	15.7
Completed Master's	40	8.2

Table 01 elucidates the socio demographic background of the respondents where total samples are distinguished by 70.5% male and 29.5% female; university level students are categorized by DU Affiliated Seven College 25.7%, National University 24.5%, Private University 19.6% and Public University 30.2%. Recognizing living area 62.8% respondents live in Dhaka city where 22.5% in village and 31.9% respondent's family income is below 15000 Taka, 39.1% in range between 15000-30000 Taka and 29% above 30000 Taka. Respondents are also classified by marital status where 90.6% are unmarried and rests of (9.4%) are married. Among the respondents 76.1% enrolled in Honor's degree, 15.7% Master's degree and 8.2% completed their master's degree program.

Table 02: Association between Educational Institution and Social Indicators of COVID-19

University	Variable	Du Affiliated Seven College	National University	Private University	Public University	Total	P
Total N (%)		N(%)=104 (21.3)	N(%)=113 (23.1)	N(%)=89 (18.2)	N(%)=183 (37.4)	N(%)=489	
Family force stopping study to get married (girls)	NO	8 (33.3)	25 (58.1)	16 (48.5)	40 (57.1)	89 (52.4)	0.179
	YES	16 (66.7)	18 (41.9)	17 (51.5)	30 (42.9)	81 (47.6)	
Spending COVID time	Above all	31 (32.3)	35 (31.2)	26 (30.6)	51 (29.0)	143 (30.5)	0.615
	By doing earning based work	4 (4.2)	7 (6.2)	5 (5.9)	19 (10.8)	35 (7.5)	
	By doing household work	15 (15.6)	16 (14.3)	11 (12.9)	27 (15.3)	69 (14.7)	
	By playing online games	1 (1.0)	1 (0.9)	5 (5.9)	5 (2.8)	12 (2.6)	
	By reading books	11 (11.5)	9 (8.0)	6 (7.1)	13 (7.4)	39 (8.3)	
	By using social media	34 (35.4)	44 (39.3)	32 (37.6)	61 (34.7)	171 (36.5)	
Engaged quarrels with parents and family during COVID	NO	83 (79.8)	86 (76.1)	61 (68.5)	118 (65.2)	348 (71.5)	0.035
	YES	21 (20.2)	27 (23.9)	28 (31.5)	63 (34.8)	139 (28.5)	
Smoking during COVID period	NO	98 (94.2)	89 (80.2)	66 (74.2)	158 (86.3)	411 (84.4)	0.001
	YES	6 (5.8)	22 (19.8)	23 (25.8)	25 (13.7)	76 (15.6)	
Family urges in getting married to recover this uncertain future	NO	82 (78.8)	90 (80.4)	76 (87.4)	140 (76.9)	388 (80.0)	0.249
	YES	22 (21.2)	22 (19.6)	11 (12.6)	42 (23.1)	97 (20.0)	
Sleeping during COVID	3-4 Hours	4 (3.8)	2 (1.8)	5 (5.6)	8 (4.4)	19 (3.9)	0.511

	4-5 Hours	5 (4.8)	8 (7.1)	2 (2.2)	8 (4.4)	23 (4.7)	
	5-6 Hours	21 (20.2)	12 (10.6)	14 (15.7)	27 (14.8)	74 (15.1)	
	6-7 Hours	26 (25.0)	25 (22.1)	19 (21.3)	50 (27.3)	120 (24.5)	
	8-10 Hours	48 (46.2)	66 (58.4)	49 (55.1)	90 (49.2)	253 (51.7)	
Used time of social media during COVID	2-3HOURS	27 (26.0)	27 (23.9)	13 (14.6)	40 (21.9)	107 (21.9)	0.004
	3-4 HOURS	19 (18.3)	25 (22.1)	14 (15.7)	37 (20.2)	95 (19.4)	
	4-5 HOURS	30 (28.8)	18 (15.9)	13 (14.6)	48 (26.2)	109 (22.3)	
	5-6 HOURS	28 (26.9)	43 (38.1)	49 (55.1)	58 (31.7)	178 (36.4)	

Table 02 demonstrates that 47.6% of the girls were forced by their family stop studying and to get married during pandemic. Most of the students spent their time during pandemic by using social media (36.5%), by reading books (8.3%), by playing online games (2.6%), by doing household work (14.7%), by doing earning based work (7.5%). In addition, 28.5% students engaged quarrels with their family and parents during pandemic ($p < 0.035$) as well as (14.6%) students involve smoking during COVID-19 pandemic ($p < 0.001$) those variables have a significant relation with educational institutions. Moreover 20% students were urged by their family to get marry during pandemic to recover this uncertain future. In During pandemic on an average sleeping hours in a day of the respondents: 3 to 4 hours (3.9%), 4 to 5 hours (4.7%), 5 to 6 hours (15.1%), 6 to 7 hours (24.5%), and majority of respondents (51.7%) were slept from 8 to 10 hours. Used time of social media during pandemic: 2 to 3 hours (21.9%), 3 to 4 hours (19.4%), 4 to 5 hours (22.3%), 5 to 6 hours (36.4%) respectively and ($p < 0.004$) which have a statistically significant relation with educational institutions.

Table 03: Association between Educational Institution and Mental Indicators of COVID-19

University	Variable	DU Affiliated Seven College	National University	Private University	Public University	Total	p
Total N (%)		N(%)=104 (21.3)	N(%)=113 (23.1)	N(%)=89 (18.2)	N(%)=183 (37.4)	N(%)=489	
Longtime closure of educational institutional created more frustration	NO	10 (9.6)	8 (7.1)	11 (12.4)	20 (10.9)	49 (10.0)	0.613
	YES	94 (90.4)	105 (92.9)	78 (87.6)	163 (89.1)	440 (90.0)	
Suicide step in yourself	NO	82 (79.6)	95 (84.1)	71 (79.8)	152 (83.1)	400 (82.0)	0.762
	YES	21 (20.4)	18 (15.9)	18 (20.2)	31 (16.9)	88 (18.0)	
Getting suggestion from mental disease expert	NO	90 (89.1)	104 (92.0)	70 (79.5)	166 (93.8)	430 (89.8)	0.003
	YES	11 (10.9)	9 (8.0)	18 (20.5)	11 (6.2)	49 (10.2)	
Taking drug for mental stress	NO	97 (94.2)	101 (90.2)	80 (89.9)	170 (93.9)	448 (92.4)	0.451

	YES	6 (5.8)	11 (9.8)	9 (10.1)	11 (6.1)	37 (7.6)	
Feeling depressed most of the time	NO	36 (34.6)	36 (31.9)	33 (37.9)	92 (50.3)	197 (40.5)	0.006
	YES	68 (65.4)	77 (68.1)	54 (62.1)	91 (49.7)	290 (59.5)	
Lost interest from preferred work	NO	27 (26.0)	19 (17.1)	17 (19.3)	59 (32.2)	122 (25.1)	0.016
	YES	77 (74.0)	92 (82.9)	71 (80.7)	124 (67.8)	364 (74.9)	
Over Sleeping	NO	39 (37.5)	28 (25.2)	17 (19.1)	56 (30.6)	140 (28.7)	0.030
	YES	65 (62.5)	83 (74.8)	72 (80.9)	127 (69.4)	347 (71.3)	
Think yourself negatively	NO	46 (44.2)	44 (38.9)	27 (30.3)	90 (49.2)	207 (42.3)	0.024
	YES	58 (55.8)	69 (61.1)	62 (69.7)	93 (50.8)	282 (57.7)	
Suffer yourself indecision	NO	37 (35.6)	26 (23.0)	28 (31.5)	81 (44.3)	172 (35.2)	0.002
	YES	67 (64.4)	87 (77.0)	61 (68.5)	102 (55.7)	317 (64.8)	
Share your mental stress	NO	52 (50.0)	46 (40.7)	35 (39.3)	80 (43.7)	213 (43.6)	0.427
	YES	52 (50.0)	67 (59.3)	54 (60.7)	103 (56.3)	276 (56.4)	
Feeling mental stress	Agree	33 (37.5)	39 (37.1)	39 (48.1)	78 (45.6)	189 (42.5)	0.005
	Disagree	5 (5.7)	8 (7.6)	8 (9.9)	5 (2.9)	26 (5.8)	
	Neutral	28 (31.8)	41 (39.0)	15 (18.5)	32 (18.7)	116 (26.1)	
	Strongly agree	20 (22.7)	15 (14.3)	17 (21.0)	48 (28.1)	100 (22.5)	
	Strongly disagree	2 (2.3)	2 (1.9)	2 (2.5)	8 (4.7)	14 (3.1)	
Mental stress has impacted daily activities	NO	11 (10.7)	10 (8.8)	9 (10.2)	26 (14.2)	56 (11.5)	0.511
	YES	92 (89.3)	103 (91.2)	79 (89.8)	157 (85.8)	431 (88.5)	
Duration of sleeping during COVID	3-4 Hours	4 (3.8)	2 (1.8)	5 (5.6)	8 (4.4)	19 (3.9)	0.511
	4-5 Hours	5 (4.8)	8 (7.1)	2 (2.2)	8 (4.4)	23 (4.7)	
	5-6 Hours	21 (20.2)	12 (10.6)	14 (15.7)	27 (14.8)	74 (15.1)	
	6-7 Hours	26 (25.0)	25 (22.1)	19 (21.3)	50 (27.3)	120 (24.5)	
	8-10 Hours	48 (46.2)	66 (58.4)	49 (55.1)	90 (49.2)	253 (51.7)	

Duration of sleeping before COVID	4-5 Hours	4 (3.8)	4 (3.5)	8 (9.0)	18 (9.8)	34 (7.0)	0.264
	5-6 Hours	39 (37.5)	38 (33.6)	37 (41.6)	57 (31.1)	171 (35.0)	
	6-7 Hours	37 (35.6)	38 (33.6)	28 (31.5)	61 (33.3)	164 (33.5)	
	7-8 Hours	24 (23.1)	33 (29.2)	16 (18.0)	47 (25.7)	120 (24.5)	
COVID affect your regular activities and studies	NO	21 (20.4)	16 (14.2)	23 (25.8)	34 (18.8)	94 (19.3)	0.215
	YES	82 (79.6)	97 (85.8)	66 (74.2)	147 (81.2)	392 (80.7)	
Mood swing for long time staying home during COVID	NO	29 (27.9)	22 (19.5)	18 (20.2)	51 (27.9)	120 (24.5)	0.242
	YES	75 (72.1)	91 (80.5)	71 (79.8)	132 (72.1)	369 (75.5)	
Feeling loneliness	NO	23 (22.1)	28 (25.0)	19 (21.3)	63 (34.6)	133 (27.3)	0.042
	YES	81 (77.9)	84 (75.0)	70 (78.7)	119 (65.4)	354 (72.7)	
Over thinking	NO	20 (19.2)	24 (21.2)	13 (14.6)	56 (30.6)	113 (23.1)	0.015
	YES	84 (80.8)	89 (78.8)	76 (85.4)	127 (69.4)	376 (76.9)	

Table 03 elucidates 90% of the respondents said that, longtime closure of educational institution created frustration among them. As a result, 18% of the respondents have taken suicide step during COVID pandemic. Only 10.2% of the respondents said that, they have taken suggestion from mental disease expert which has a statistically significant relation between the educational institution and mental disease expert during pandemic ($p < 0.003$). In addition, 7.6% of the respondents have taken drug for being mental stress during pandemic as well as 59.5% respondents feeling depressed most of the time ($p < 0.006$). Moreover, 74.9% respondents lost interest from their preferred work ($p < 0.016$). 71.3% respondents were oversleeping ($p < 0.030$), 57.7% think themselves negatively ($p < 0.024$), 64.8% suffer themselves in indecision ($p < 0.002$), 42.5% feel mental stress ($p < 0.005$), 72.7% feeling loneliness ($p < 0.042$), 76.9% over thinking ($p < 0.015$), students monthly expense money (49.5%) 3000 to 5000 taka (34.9%) 6000 to 8000 taka and 15.6% is 9000 to 15000 respectively ($p < 0.001$). A statistically significant association was found between those variables and the educational institutions. Moreover, 56.4% of the respondents shared their mental stress with friends, teachers and family members. In addition, 88.5% of the respondent thought that, mental stress has impacted their daily activities during pandemic. Before pandemic majority of the respondents (35%) daily sleeping was 5 to 6 hours but in during pandemic 51.7% of the respondents daily sleeping was 8 to 10 hours. This pandemic affected 80.7% of the respondent's daily activities as well as 75.5% of the respondents felt mood swing for longtime staying at home during pandemic.

Discussion

This study has been carried out to investigate the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the Bangladeshi university students (Dhaka university affiliated seven college, national university, private university, and public university) with a great focus on social and mental health indicators. For disseminating social impacts of COVID-19, this study analyzed student's family relationship, family force in stopping study to get married (girls), spending COVID time, smoking status, duration of sleeping and social media usage (Facebook) during COVID period as social indicators. Along with this student's mental health aspects (mental stress, frustration, depression, thinking about suicide, over sleeping and thinking, negative thinking, mood swing, loneliness, indecision problem, taking drug for mental stress relief, losing interest from preferred work and duration of sleeping during & before COVID-19 pandemic etc.) have been analyzed to draw a clear scenario of mental health impacts of COVID-19. This study results shows that most of the students spent their time during pandemic by using social media (Facebook) (36.5%), reading books (8.3%), playing online games (2.6%), doing household work (14.7%), doing earning based work (7.5%). These findings well evidenced by other studies that showed people are using social media more often, and university students in Bangladesh reported a 28.3% total Facebook addiction rate (Ripon et al., 2022; Hutchinson, 2019). Another study results found that 54% students use social networking sites including Facebook, Messenger, Instagram, Snapchat, Whatsapp, and others for longer than four hours each day (Piya et al., 2022). These results are inconsistent with other study which found that 39% students were mostly engaged in solo activities, 42% of students were involved in religious activities, whereas 43.9% of students watched TV, 46% of students read and wrote, and 49% of students engaged in family and friend activities

(Rezvi et al., 2022).

This study results demonstrates that during pandemic girls (47.6%) were forced by their family stop studying to get married. In addition, students engaged quarrels with their family and parents during pandemic (28.5%) as well as students involve smoking during COVID-19 pandemic (14.6%). Study result elucidates that students use social media during pandemic, 2 to 3 hours (21.9%), 3 to 4 hours (19.4%), 4 to 5 hours (22.3%), and 5 to 6 hours (36.4%). This is in line with results from other studies depicting during the pandemic, the average time spent on social media (Facebook) in a day was: 0 to 5 hours 0.74%, 6 to 10 hours 10.18%, and 11 hours or more 7.40% (Ripon et al., 2022). Consistent with other study noted that on average, students used to spend roughly 144 minutes every day on social media (Broadband Search, 2019). The study result shows that longtime closure of educational institution created frustration among students (90%) and for that they have taken suicide step during COVID pandemic (18%). This finding is consistent with prior research demonstrating student's thought (9.76%) about suicide at least once in this pandemic situation (Ripon et al., 2022). This study results illustrates that during COVID-19 pandemic, students lost their interest from their preferred work (74.9%) and most of the students acquired the bad habit of over sleeping (71.3%) & over thinking (76.9%). They suffer from indecision problem (64.8%), feeling mental stress (42.5%), loneliness (72.7%) and depression (59.5%). A prior study explored that amid the COVID-19 epidemic, 19.81% of students report feeling detached from their friends and peers, 19.11% report feeling lonely, and 24.20 percent report feeling depressed (Ripon et al., 2022). Another study results found that when they assessed student depression levels during the COVID-19 epidemic, 7.1%, 11.2%, 26.7%, and 28.9% had severe, moderately severe, moderate, and mild depression, respectively (Piya et al., 2022). This is in line with different studies that conclude that COVID-19 primarily affects stress and anxiety levels, as well as depressive illnesses (Rossi et al., 2020; Huang & Zhao, 2020; Usher et al., 2020; Gómez-García et al., 2022; Chi et al., 2020; Ihm et al., 2021). Consistent study results found that approximately 38%, 27%, and 18% of public university students in Bangladesh experienced depression, severe anxiety, and moderate stress, respectively (Rahman, PhD et al., 2021; Rahman et al., 2022).

This study demonstrated that 88.5% of the respondent thought that, mental stress has impacted their daily activities during pandemic. A previous study also explored that 51% of the respondents said that the abrupt discontinuity in their education caused by COVID-19 had a severe influence on their lives and their studies, while 34.1% respondents reported that the discontinuity had a highly unfavorable impact on their life and academics (Goldstein, 2020). Our study results shows that before the COVID-19 pandemic a signification portion of students (35%) average daily sleeping was 5 to 6 hours but in during pandemic 51.7% of the respondents daily sleeping was 8 to 10 hours. So it increases 1.5 times than the time of before pandemic. This finding is consistent with another literature, in which it was found that prior to the pandemic, just 1.5% of participants were oversleeping, but during COVID-19, the average daily sleep time was 7 to 9 hours, and 20.5% of individuals are currently doing so (Marler et al., 2021). This pandemic affected 80.7% of the respondent's daily activities as well as 75.5% of the respondents felt mood swing for longtime staying at home during pandemic. These findings are also well documented in other

literature, showing that a large majority (70%) believed that the lockdown had hampered students' work or studies (Leal Filho et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Due to COVID-19 pandemic, people from all corners of the society especially students in Bangladesh have been suffered a lot. Student's academics, daily routines and their normal life were hampered mostly where student's mental health is negatively impacted by home quarantine, physical/spatial distance and other constraints. It's noticeable that most of the students spent their time during pandemic by using social media (Facebook), reading books, playing online games doing household work and doing earning based works in some cases. An alarming portion of students (girls) were forced by their family stop studying to get married. In addition, students engaged quarrels with their family and parents as well as students involve in smoking during COVID-19 pandemic. Along with these, during COVID-19 pandemic students suffer from frustration, indecision problem, mental stress, loneliness, mood swing and even they tried to commit suicide at that time. Most of the students acquired the bad habit of over sleeping & over thinking and lost their interest from their preferred work also. The government of Bangladesh has been taken very insufficient initiatives to diminish the sufferings of students and to return the students to normal life. So government should take necessary steps to overcome these problems.

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